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EMPOWERING ATTITUDES IN THE FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Ableism is the specific prejudice against people with disabilities. Even after the implementation of various laws aimed at inclusion, it is still possible to see barriers that prevent people with disabilities from participating in society. Among these barriers is the attitudinal barrier, which is considered to be attitudes or behaviors that prevent or hinder the social participation of people with disabilities on equal terms. Many attitudinal barriers occur within the family environment, due to a lack of information. Empowerment in family relationships often manifests itself implicitly, in a protectionist way, when they consider their disabled family members to be incapable, developing words and actions that frustrate the development of their autonomy and when they disrespect their desires and emotions, taking away their right to respond to their wishes and desires, as if they had no will of their own, no voice and no turn to resolve situations in their lives. Society must learn to see people with disabilities as fellow human beings and not as inferior beings. And this learning must begin at home, including with the disabled person's family members, who tend to overprotect them.